

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetics

Contribution of IR crosses to improved cultivars for irrigated rice in Latin America

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Adoption of modern semidwarf rice varieties in Latin America began in the late 1960s with the introduction of IR8. Although yield gains were impressive, grain quality was below regional standards. This stimulated additional introductions and breeding work to select locally adapted materials.

After nearly 20 yr of germplasm improvement work, modern semidwarf varieties are planted on 31 % of the rice area and contribute 56% of total Latin American rice production. For irrigated rice, 80% of the area and production are modern varieties. International collaboration through the International Network for the Genetic Evaluation of Rice (INGER, formerly IRTP) has been a major force behind these technological improvements.

To determine the contribution of IR materials to the improvement of irrigated rice in Latin America, the pedigrees of 143 cultivars released 1971-89 were ana-

lyzed: 85% had at least one IR line in their parentage.

Chile was the only country with no cultivar showing IR parentage, probably because of subtropical growing conditions. Other countries whose materials had low IR input were the traditional exporters, Surinam and Uruguay.

Table 1. IR breeding lines in the parentage of irrigated rice cultivars released in Latin America, 1971-89.

IR line	Cultivar name	Country, year of release
IR442	Huallaga	Peru, 1972
	BR2	Brazil, 1978
IR579	IR100	Nicaragua, 1973
	INIAP2	Ecuador, 1971
	Navolato A7 1	Mexico, 1971
IR665	IR665	Brazil, 1976
IR822	CR1113	Costa Rica, 1974
IR837	Bamoa A75	Mexico, 1975
	Piedras Negras A74	Mexico, 1974
IR841	IR841	Brazil, 1974
	EMPASC 104	Brazil, 1985
IR930	BR-IRGA 408	Brazil, 1975
	Chancay	Peru, 1972
	Cica 4	Colombia, 1971
	INIAP6	Ecuador, 1972
	Naylamp	Peru, 1971
IR1055	N	Guyana, 1975
IR1529	IR1529	Cuba, 1978
IR2058	Pesagro 102	Brazil, 1983
IR2153	Juma 62	Dominican Republic, 1986
IR4570	PA-3	Peru, 1984
IR5853	Saavedra	Bolivia, 1987
IR8208	Pesagro 101	Brazil, 1983
IR18348	INIAP11	Ecuador, 1989

In rice varieties from the rest of the region, 24 cultivars were direct selections of IR lines (Table 1). About two-thirds of them were released 1971-78. IR930 was named in five countries. Navolato A71 (IR579) in Mexico and INIAP II (IR18348) in Ecuador are the most widely grown direct IR selections. Since 1978, most of the IR line contributions have been as parents in local crosses.

Fifty-two IR lines have been used in national breeding programs; the most frequently found were IR8, IR579, and IR930 (Table 2). Some 90% of the 2.1 million ha of irrigated favorable rainfed rice area of Latin America is currently planted to cultivars with IR8 in their parentage. □

Table 2. IR lines most frequently found in the parentage of Latin American irrigated rice cultivars, 1971-89.

IR line	Progenitor of released cultivars	Genetic contribution per cultivar ^a	
		Mean	Maximum
IR8	76.2	0.36	0.75
IR262	26.6	0.50	0.50
IR579	36.4	0.29	1.00
IR661	9.1	0.22	0.50
IR665	34.3	0.28	1.00
IR841	16.8	0.17	1.00
IR930	51.0	0.38	1.00

^a Assuming 50% contribution of each parent in a single cross. A contribution of 1.0 indicates that the IR line was released as a cultivar.

Breeding methods—hybrid rice

Photosynthesis and respiration in rice hybrids

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Heterosis in photosynthesis in F₁ rice hybrids is not well established; it is considered to be mostly cross-specific. We studied heterosis in photosynthetic rate (Pn) and maintenance respiration (L_{MR}) in IR54152 A/IR54 and V20 A/

IR36 at the vegetative (35 d after planting) and flowering stages during the 1990 dry season. MR provides energy for the biochemical and physiological state of established tissues. It differs considerably among cultivars.

The hybrids, their restorers, and check variety Swarnaprabha were planted in pots. Pn in the second leaf at the vegetative stage and in the flag leaf at flowering were measured by LI-6000 at full sunlight (about 1200 μE/m² per s). MR was

measured by differential respirometer as CO₂ evolution rate on excised leaves after incubation in the dark for 8 h.

The hybrids showed higher Pn and MR than their restorers at both growth stages (see table). Pn was similar, but MR was higher in the hybrid with IR36 than in the hybrid with IR54. Both hybrids had higher Pn and MR than Swarnaprabha.

Heterosis over restorer was consistently higher in V20 A/IR36. Heterosis for Pn was higher at the vegetative stage than at flowering; differences in heterosis for MR were only marginal. Standard

heterosis was also high in V20 A/IR36, especially for MR at flowering.

Pn/MR in IR54752 A/IR54 showed marginal positive heterosis at the vegetative stage and was negative at flowering. Both hybrids showed negative

standard heterosis over Swarnaprabha in Pn/MR, especially at flowering.

These results suggest that selecting restorers to reduce MR and improve Pn and Pn/MR would increase photosynthetic productivity. □

Photosynthetic rate (Pn) and maintenance respiration (MR)^a of F₁ rice hybrids in Cuttack, India, 1990 dry season.^b

Hybrid	Vegetative			Flowering		
	Pn	MR	Pn/MR	Pn	MR	Pn/MR
IR54752 A/IR54	45.3 (24)	1.66 (17)	27.2 (6)	33.4 (6)	1.23 (19)	27.1 (-11)
V20 A/IR36	46.1 (36)	1.80 (25)	25.6 (9)	34.7 (26)	1.46 (23)	23.7 (2)
Swarnaprabha	36.2	1.28	28.3	29.6	0.90	32.8
LSD(0.05)	3.4	0.11		1.9	0.12	
Standard heterosis						
IR54752 A/IR54	25	29	4	13	36	-17
V20 A/IR36	27	40	-10	17	62	-28

^aPn and MR in mg CO₂/dm² per h. ^bFigures in parentheses = heterosis over restorer.

Effect of low light on F₁ rice hybrids

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F₁ rice hybrids are reported to be more productive than elite conventional varieties even under such stresses as drought and salinity. Low light is another major constraint to rice production during the rainy season.

We studied tolerance for low light in hybrids IR54752 A/IR54 and V20 A/IR36 and their restorers, with standard checks Ratna and Swarnaprabha during 1990 dry season. The crop was grown in 1.2-m² field plots at 15- × 10-cm plant spacing and fertilized with 80 kg N/ha.

Low light (50% sunlight) condition was imposed from 40 d after planting to harvest by shading with wood screens. Controls were maintained under normal sunlight (about 420 cal/cm² per d). The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Growth durations were 128 d in all treatments.

The hybrids showed positive heterosis in total dry matter and yield over the restorer parent under low light only (see table).

Yield and heterosis in yield were higher for IR54752 A/IR54 than for V20 A/IR36.

Effect of low light (50% of normal) from 40 d after planting to harvest on dry matter and yield of F₁ rice hybrid restorers and check varieties. Cuttack, India.

Cultivar	Total dry matter (g/m ²)		Yield (g/m ²)	
	Full light	Low light	Full light	Low light
Hybrid				
IR54752 A/IR54	985	643	418	206
V20 A/IR36	853	471	345	167
Restorers				
IR54	993	537	426	179
IR36	853	427	400	164
Checks				
Ratna	803	358	354	144
Swarnaprabha	928	597	480	243
Mean	902	506	403	183
LSD(0.05)				
Variety	99		17	
Treatment	57		44	
Variety × treatment	ns		ns	
Heterosis over restorer				
IR54752 A/IR54	-1	19	-2	15
V20 A/IR36	0	11	-13	2
Standard heterosis				
IR54152 A/IR54 vs				
Ratna	22	79	18	43
Swarnaprabha	6	8	-13	-15
V20 A/IR36 vs				
Ratna	6	33	-3	16
Swarnaprabha	8	-20	-28	-31

This could be associated with the higher yield potential of restorer IR54. The hybrids also showed strong standard heterosis over Ratna under low light, but negative heterosis in yield over Swarnaprabha, a low light-tolerant variety. □

Analysis of heterotic relationships among quantitative characters of hybrid rice

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In 1987, we used 6 male sterile lines and 12 fertility restorer lines to make 72 F₁ hybrid combinations. A field experiment Apr-Oct 1988 was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications, with 30 plants per plot. Row and hill spacing was 17 × 23 cm. The center five plants in each plot were sampled.

Eleven characters were analyzed (Table 1): days to heading (DH), culm number/plant (CN), panicle length (PL, cm), plant height (PH, cm), total spikelet number/panicle (TSN), filled spikelet number/panicle (FSN), filled spikelet percentage (FSP), 1,000-grain weight (GW, g), biological yield/plant (BY, g), grain-straw ratio (GSR), and grain yield/plant (GY, g). Heterosis was estimated for each character as

$$H = F_1 - (P_1 + P_2)/2$$

Correlation coefficient and stepwise regression analysis were used to estimate relationships among characters.

Correlations varied with character combinations; 31 were significant (Table 1). In the F₁ hybrids, correlations of DH to TSN and FSN; CN to BY; PL to PH, FSN, GW, and BY; PH to TSN, FSN, and BY; TSN to FSN and BY, FSN to FSP, BY, and GSR; FSP to GSR; GW to GSR; and CY to CN, PL, PH, FSN, FSP, GW, BY, and GSR were positive and significant; those of DH to GW, CN to TSN and FSN, and TSN to FSP, GW, and GSR were negative and significant.

Some of the character combinations had more or less the same correlation trends, except that more character combinations showed significant correlations in the F₁ hybrids than in the parents, particularly GSR, which had negative correlation (although nonsignificant) in the parents with PL, FSN, FSP, GW, and BY but showed positive correlation